

THE CONTRIBUTION OF BERNARA RAKHIMOVNA TO THE FORMATION OF THE UZBEK THEATER SCENE

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Annotation: *This article discusses the results of the great contribution of Bernara Rakhimovna to the development and progress of the Uzbek theatrical stage in dance. We can see the arrival of ballet in Uzbekistan and how it is perceived and interpreted around the world through a small historical page.*

Key words: *dance, stage, theatre, ballet, opera, composer, Bakhchisaray fountain, Bronze Horseman, Masquerade, creativity, artist, music, classics.*

Bernara Rakhimovna was directly involved in the formation of the Uzbek theater scene, and her performances were welcomed by the Moscow Bolshoi Theater.

His parents also worked in the theater. His father, Rakhim Medzhidovich, was the director of the theater for many years. As a child, he devoted himself to the stage. In Uzbekistan there was an opera theater named after I. Sverdlov. Operas were performed there both in Uzbek and in Russian with the participation of Russian artists. Posters in front of the theater were also announced in two different languages. His father, Rakhim Medzhidovich, was the director of the Uzbek troupe, and Vladimir Shneiderman was the director of the Russian troupe. So they will work together.

And in 1947, the Opera and Ballet Theater named after Alisher Navoi was opened. Both troupes were united according to the project and in the building built under the direction of academician Alexei Shchusev. The building was so strong that even during the great earthquake of 1966 in Tashkent there were no cracks in the wall. When the theater merged, my father became a theater director. And he worked in this theater for 15 years.

She was a five-year-old girl when her father Sverdlov brought her to the theater. Bernara Rakhimovna plays the role of chickens there. The mother bird ballerina makes an arabesque and the chicks come out from under the arabesque.

Bernara Rakhimovna says that my youth in this profession coincided with the war years. At that time, most people had to move to other places. All artists lived in Tashkent during the war. For example, Nikita Bogoslovsky lived in my house. In front of my parents. Our neighbors Boris Andreev and Mark Bernes were with us.

And we lived in a small two-room apartment, and my mother gave the second room to Bogoslovsky. And then he wrote "Dark Night" from the movie "Two Soldiers" at our place! Nikita Vladimirovich lived with us for five years. says Bernard.

She resisted becoming a ballerina until her mother passed away (her mother lived to be 105). After she was not accepted into ballet, she entered the Tashkent Choreographic School. From there, the ballerina of the Bolshoi Theater of the USSR, People's Artist of the USSR Raisa Struchkova took him to study in Moscow.

Koyukhova Maria Alekseevna was rude to Bernard when she first saw her. Because she looked like a simple country girl. Marya Alekseevna said: "Why did you come here in such a state? Who goes to the brook with forty kokils?" But these words did not offend him, on the contrary, they inspired him very much.

Having settled in a hostel, he called Tashkent to his home: he spoke with his father and asked him to pick him up. But dad: No! Because you chose this profession - you went there, now you have to study! Otherwise, if you go home, your mother will win. So Bernara stayed there to continue her studies. His father and mother lived in Tashkent until the end of the war.

I came to Moscow when I was 9 years old. And I studied there until 1956. Our course passed all exams for the first time - physics, geometry and chemistry. Maris Liepa studied with me in the same class. And he laughed at me: "Stop this education! Practice like I do - only ballet! She studied only ballet, and I studied theory. So I really studied there. It was difficult for me. Our classes started at 8 am and ended at 8 pm.

Her first strong performance was the solo part in the ballet The Nutcracker. There they danced to the festive waltz of the last act. But this was already for the senior classes - not for kids, but when they were in 7-8 grades.

The Uzbek theater called Bernard a ballerina-soloist. Although he spent most of his time in the USSR.

Her first roles were in Tashkent, where she danced Pushkin's The Fountain of Bakhchisarai, her first ballet. The second was Pushkin's The Bronze Horseman by Reinhold Gliere.

In 1959, he brought Lermontov's ballet Masquerade and composer Lev Laputin to Moscow. When he saw the posters in Moscow, he thought: "Did the Uzbeks really bring the Masquerade?"

The great Galina Ulanova came to the Bolshoi, and Bernara Rakhimovna took part in all four performances. They even played the fifth performance. There were so many people at that time that they were so excited that they couldn't seem to get enough of it. In other words, the Uzbek performance "Masquerade" made a splash.

On the way back from Moscow, Pravda published an article titled "Vertigo..." which encouraged them to take the next step. Praised as "Uzbek dizziness"! Thus, this inspired the following workflow.

The great theatrical choreographer Anatoly Kuznetsov arrived and staged the ballet Don Juan to the music of Leonid Feigin. Great ballet, just great. There Bernara Rakhimovna played the role of Donna Anna. And again they brought the goods to Moscow. Khrushchev was leaving at that time, and Brezhnev arrived. This was in 1964.

In the same year, L. I. Brezhnev invited artists and said to Bernard: "How did you raise the performances in this theater! You brought new productions, new names to the theatre. Did you perform as artists of the Bolshoi Theater? L. I. Brezhnev valued them so much that how much less space do you have than in the Bolshoi Theater of the USSR? He stressed that the Tashkent theater should be awarded the title of Senior.

I think it was the biggest award for the theatre. Since 1966, its name sounded like the Uzbek State Academic Bolshoi Theater. There were 836 theaters in the USSR. There are three of them: in Moscow, Minsk and Tashkent.

The creative life of Bernara Rakhimovna is connected with Russia. He knew both Russian ballet and Russian classics. He based his biography on the Russian classics in general. In the "Stranger" block, then the ballet "Turgenev", "How good, how fresh the roses were."

The next ballet performance was a biographical ballet performance. That is, the scene of the old Turgenev, the last part of the third scene. On stage, his life is depicted with Pauline Viardot. This is for Russian ballets (later Anna Karenina). Bernara Rakhimovna was awarded the title of People's Artist of the USSR in 1973, and in 1982 - the State Prize of the USSR. All biography in Russian. Silver or even gold ribbon of Russian classics.

Bernara Rakhimovna was close friends with Maya Plisetskaya. It's not even friendship, it's a wonderful "Great Duality". Bernara Rakhimovna Maya Mikhailovna met during a tour in Tashkent. Then Plisetskaya staged Anna Karenina. Taking advantage of my acquaintance, I asked permission to stage this ballet. I also say that, due to my age, I could no longer dance with girls, and I didn't want to. Maya Mikhailovna: "We must act!" The directors who were preparing the horror came to me.

Plisetskaya arrived at that time for the premiere and shared her impressions with her husband Rodion Shchedrin. Then Bernara Rakhimovna brought Anna Karenina to Moscow, to the Bolshoi Theatre. And that was courage! I wonder how Bernara Rakhimovna persuaded him?! But this was with the consent of Plisetskaya and Shchedrin.

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